

***Thymus fedtschenkoi* essential oils composition and their antioxidant activity; A comparative study on hydrodistillation and solvent free microwave extraction**

Fereshteh Nematollahi

Department of Chemistry, East Tehran Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran

E-mail: fnematollahi@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 26 September 2018, accepted 01 November 2018

In the present project, the essential oil of *Thymus fedtschenkoi*, was obtained both by hydrodistillation (HD) procedure and the solvent free microwave extraction (SFME) method; and then, the extracts were analyzed by the GC-MS technic. Thymol (51.6%), geraniol (8.3%) and *p*-cymene (7.3%) were the main constituents among twenty-one identified components (97.6% of total oil) in SFME method; while, thirty-two compounds (98.2% of the oil) were characterized in hydrodistilled oil containing: thymol (38.6%), geraniol (15.8%) and γ -terpinene (7.3%) as major compounds. Also, the antioxidant activity of each extract was investigated using radical scavenging of DPPH radicals. The values of IC_{50} were 2635.85 and 462.69 mg L⁻¹ for HD and SFME approaches obtained oils, respectively.

Keywords: *Thymus fedtschenkoi*, essential oil, antioxidant, hydrodistillation, FSME.

Introduction

Essential oils which refer to volatile constituents of plant secondary metabolites and are extracted from different parts of herbs, usually, exhibit important biological properties such as antimicrobial and antioxidant activities¹. Also, the essential oils are widely used in pharmaceutical, agricultural and cosmetic industries². There are different procedures for extraction of those oils such as distillation (containing hydro distillation and steam distillation), cold press and maceration (solvent extraction)³. It should be mentioned that the microwave instruments not only provide a contactless heating source (which enables more effective and selective heating procedure); but also, increase the heat transfer speed and accelerate the energy transfer, start-up, response to heating control, reduce thermal gradient, equipment size and operation units⁴. Also, the solvent free microwave extraction (SFME) method is a green chemistry procedure to extract the natural product. This is a hybrid method of microwave heating and distillation done in atmospheric pressure with adding any additional water⁵.

The genus *thymus* belongs to Lamiaceae family with 215 species in the world and almost fourteen of them exist in Iran. *Thymus carmanicus*, *Thymus daenensis*, *Thymus persicus* and *Thymus trautvetteri* are endemic to Iran flora⁶.

Their species are used in folk medicine due to their biological and pharmaceutical properties of their essential oils which are rich in phenolic compounds such as carvacrol and thymol⁷. *Thymus* essential oils and extracts are widely used in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, perfume industry and also for flavoring and preservation of food products as antioxidant agents⁸. The chemical composition of essential oil of *thymus* species which grown in Iran have been interesting to study by researchers due to its high content of bio-active phenolic compounds (see Table 1). This paper deals with comparison of chemical composition of *Thymus fedtschenkoi*

Table 1. Chemical compositions of *Thymus* species from Iran in last decade

<i>Thymus</i> species	Main constituents	Refs.
<i>T. daenensis</i>	Thymol (70.8%), carvacrol (6.3%)	9
<i>T. vulgaris</i> L.	Thymol (35.5%), carvacrol (4.4%)	10
<i>T. fedtschenkoi</i>	Carvacrol (69.04%), thymol (5.95%)	11
<i>T. trautvetteri</i>	Carvacrol (54.02%), thymol (9.29%)	11
<i>T. pubescens</i>	Carvacrol (13.85%), α -terpineol (11.49%)	11
<i>T. pubescens</i>	Carvacrol (33.49%), thymol (14.19)	12
<i>T. daenensis</i>	Thymol (77.62%)	13
<i>T. carmanicus</i>	Carvacrol (65.52%), <i>p</i> -cymene (13.21%)	13
<i>T. vulgaris</i>	Thymol (54.26%), γ -terpinene (9.50%)	14
<i>T. carmanicus</i>	Thymol (40.8%), carvacrol (24.8%)	15

essential oils obtained by hydrodistillation and solvent free microwave extraction (SFME). Moreover, the capacity of the extract as the antioxidant is reported for the first time.

Experimental

Plant material: The areal parts of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* were collected from Khoy (Latitude 38.5503°N, Longitude 44.9522°E), Province of Ardebil in July 2015 at flowering stage. The plant material was authenticated by Dr. V. Mozafarri in Research Institute of Forests and Rangelands (R.I.F.R.), Tehran, Iran. A voucher specimen was kept in the herbarium of R.I.F.R. They were dried in shade and grinded by a Ika MF 10.1 mill and kept in 4°C.

Essential oil extraction: The *Thymus fedtschenkoi* essential oil was extracted by hydrodistillation and solvent free microwave extraction (SFME)¹⁶. Hydrodistillation was done according to European pharmacopeia using a Clevenger type apparatus. 100 g of grinded air dried *Thymus fedtschenkoi* plant material was distilled for 4.5 h. The pale yellowish oil (0.52% w/w, yields) was dried on anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and kept in 4°C in dark vial.

SFME was performed using a milestone microsynth microwave oven with a microwave reactor 2455 MHz with a maximum delivered power of 1000 W variable in 10 W increments. Temperature was controlled using a ATC-300 shielded thermocouple. 50 g of air dried of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* materials were soaked in deionized water. The excess of water was removed after 30 min and the moisturized plant tissues were placed in a two-neck flask and located in microwave cavity. A Clevenger system was used outside of microwave cavity in order to condense the distillate continuously. The SFME procedure was performed at optimum condition (extraction time, 30 min, Microwave power, 600 watts and type of sample: crushed) and at atmospheric pressure by heating the moisturized tissues at 100°C. The pale yellowish oil (0.64% w/w, yields) was dried by anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and kept in dark vial in 4°C.

Identification and quantification of the essential oil compounds: The identification of the constituents of each essential oil was performed using gas chromatography (GC) and (GC-MS). The GC analysis was done using a Hewlett-Packard 6970 B instrument equipped with a polar HP-5 column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID, film thickness 0.25 μm), flame ionization (FID) detector and split (1:30) injector. The oven temperature was

programmed from 60 to 230°C in increments of 5°C/min. Injector and detector temperatures were set 230 and 250°C, respectively. N₂ (1 ml/min) was used as carrier gas.

GC-MS analysis was performed using a Hewlett-Packard 6890 GC which coupled to a HP-5973 mass selective detector equipped with a HP-5MS ((30 m × 0.25 mm ID, film thickness 0.25 μm). Injector and transfer line temperatures were set 230 and 280°C, respectively. He (99.999% at 1 ml/min) used as carrier gas. MS spectra ionization energy was 70 eV. MS spectra were achieved in 40–500 amu mass range with 1 s as scan time.

Characterizations of essential oil components were done by comparison of achieved MS spectra and their relative retention indices (RRI), relative to those of n-alkanes C8-C20, with 275 Wiley MS database and which are in authentic reference¹⁷.

Free radical scavenging capacity (RSC): Antioxidant activity of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* essential oil obtained by hydro distillation and SFME procedures was measured in term of radical scavenging capacity using stable 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH). 0.5 ml of a concentration series (100, 250, 500, 750 and 1000 μg ml⁻¹) of metabolic solution of essential oils was added to a 2.5 ml of 0.2 mM methanolic solution of DPPH which shaken vigorously and incubated in dark at room temperature. The absorbance of each sample was measured at 517 nm (using a Varian Carry 300 UV-Vis spectrophotometer). RSC% of essential oils concentration was calculated using below equation:

$$\text{RSC}(\%) = 100 \times [(A_{\text{blank}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{sample}}]$$

The concentration of essential oil which causes fifty percent inhibition (IC₅₀) was calculated by linear regression analysis from the obtained amount of RSC for each concentration. Butyl hydroxyl toluene (BHT) as standard antioxidant compound¹⁸.

Results and discussion

The percentages of essential oil compositions were determined by GC and GC-MS according their MS spectra and RRIs similarity to authentic references and their GC peak areas. As shown in Table 2, thirty-two compounds representing 98.2% of total oil, with thymol (38.6%), geraniol (15.8%), γ-terpinene (7.3%), p-cymene (6.4%) and geranyl format (5.0%) as major constituents, were characterized in

Table 2. Percentage composition of hydrodistilled and FSME obtained oils

Compound	RRI	Hydrodistillation (%)	FSME (%)
α-Thujene	931	0.4	–
α-Pinene	939	1.0	0.3
Camphene	953	0.9	0.7
β-Pinene	980	0.4	–
Myrecene	991	1.8	0.9
α-Phellandrene	1005	0.4	–
α-Terpinene	1018	1.8	0.5
p-Cymene	1026	6.4	7.3
1,8-Cineol	1033	2.5	2.6
(Z)-β-Ocimene	1040	0.2	–
(E)-β-Ocimene	1050	0.3	–
α-Terpinene	1062	7.3	3.7
cis-Sabinene hydrate	1068	0.2	–
Terpinolene	1088	0.3	–
Linalool	1098	0.5	0.7
Camphor	1143	1.2	1.6
Borneol	1165	2.3	2.5
Terpinen-4-ol	1177	1.1	1.0
α-Terpineol	1189	0.6	–
Nerol	1228	–	3.2
Citronellol	1229	0.3	–
Thymol, methyl ether	1235	3.8	1.7
Neral	1240	0.4	0.6
Geraniol	1255	15.8	8.3
Bornyl acetate	1285	0.2	–
Thymol	1290	38.6	51.6
Carvacrol	1298	–	3.5
Geranyl formate	1300	5.0	–
Geranyl acetate	1383	–	2.2
β-Caryophyllene	1418	1.7	3.0
β-Bisabolene	1509	0.2	0.3
δ-Cadinene	1524	0.1	–
Caryophyllene oxide	1581	0.2	0.6
Heptacecane	1700	1.7	–
Eicosane	2000	0.5	–
Identified compounds (%)		98.2	97.6

hydrodistilled essential oil. Twenty-one components representing 97.6% of total oil were identified in the oil extracted by SFME procedure with thymol (51.6%), geraniol (8.3%), p-cymene (7.3%), γ-terpinene (3.7%) and carvacrol (3.5%) as main constituents. As mention in Table 2, these oils were characterized by high percentage of thymol and carvacrol as the other *Thymus* species which investigated in Iran.

As shown in Table 3, the hydrodistilled and FSME extracted oils contain hydrocarbon monoterpenes (21.1% and 13.4%), oxygenated monoterpenes (72.5% and 79.5%), hydrocarbon sesquiterpenes (2.0% and 3.3%), oxygenated sesquiterpenes (0.2% and 0.6%) and other compounds (2.2 and 0.0%), respectively.

As literary survey showed that, thymol and carvacrol were the main compounds in the oil of *Thymus* species which grown in Iran. This study has revealed that thymol (38.6 and 51.6%) was the main component in the hydrodistilled and SFME essential oil, respectively.

The essential oil of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* was investigated for its antioxidant activity via DPPH radical scavenging method. The color change from violet to yellow was indicated the reduction of DPPH radicals to diphenylpicrylhydrazine. The DPPH radical scavenging capacity (RSC%) of each metabolic solution of essential oils which obtained by each procedure and BHT as standard substance, were shown in Table 4.

Fig. 1. RSC% for different concentrations of essential oils and BHT.

Table 3. Main composition class of hydrodistilled and FSME extracted oils

	Hydrocarbon monoterpenes (%)	Oxygenated monoterpenes (%)	Hydrocarbon sesquiterpenes (%)	Oxygenated sesquiterpenes (%)	Other compounds (%)
Hydrodistillation	21.2	72.5	2.0	0.2	2.2
SFME	13.4	79.5	3.3	0.6	0.0

Table 4. The amounts of RSC% for each extracted oil and BHT

Concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Hydrodistilled oil (RSC%)	SFME obtained oil (RSC%)	BHT (RSC%)
100	9.93 \pm 0.62	13.07 \pm 0.20	17.91 \pm 0.37
250	22.28 \pm 0.46	30.99 \pm 0.34	44.07 \pm 0.28
500	56.42 \pm 0.14	60.37 \pm 0.31	70.74 \pm 0.22
750	79.62 \pm 0.38	80.55 \pm 0.73	84.86 \pm 0.23
1000	79.66 \pm 0.14	82.04 \pm 0.32	92.98 \pm 0.34

pears as a good alternative for the extraction of essential oils from aromatic plants. The results showed that the oil of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* could be extracted by solvent free microwave extraction method instead of the traditional hydrodistillation procedure; as this method performs at shorter extraction time with the minimum amounts of chemical changes like hydrolysis and isomerization.

Furthermore, the radical scavenging activity investiga-

Fig. 2. RSC% against the concentration of (A): hydro distilled oil, (B): FSME extracted oil and (C): BHT concentration.

Fig.1 shows the RSC% amounts against each oils concentration. The IC_{50} values of each oil was calculated using the regression equation of RSC% against the concentration of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* essential oil curve (Fig. 2) at RSC% = 50.

Therefore, the amounts of IC_{50} were 515.26, 456.75 and 344.39 mg L^{-1} for hydrodistilled oil, SFME obtained oil and BHT, respectively. In contrast to the other reports on radical scavenging capacity of thymus essential oil from Iran, the IC_{50} for *Thymus vulgaris* was 450.11 mg L^{-1} with carvacrol (85.94%) and thymol (3.33%) as the main constituents¹⁹ and the IC_{50} for *Thymus caramanicus* was determined 124.3 mg L^{-1} with carvacrol (85.9%), thymol (3.3%) as the main constituents²⁰.

As seen in our study and the other reports on antioxidant activity, a relationship can be between the RSC% values and the amount of carvacrol which is a phenolic compound in the thyme essential oils.

Conclusions

The SFME method yields essential oils with higher amounts of oxygenated compounds, and allows saving costs, in terms of time, energy and plant material. On the other hand, it could be considered as a green technology and ap-

tion on the oil of *Thymus fedtschenkoi* showed an acceptable antioxidant activity of SFME compared to butyl hydroxyl toluene (BHT) (as a standard antioxidant), and it could be due to existence of carvacrol and thymol in *Thymus* species.

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to Dr. Kambiz Larjani (Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University) for the GC-MS analysis.

References

1. F. Bakkali, S. Averbeck, D. Averbeck and M. Idaomar, *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 2008, **46**, 446.
2. S. Najafian, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2014, **52**, 575.
3. J. C. Calo, P. G. Crandall, C. A. O'Bryan and S. C. Ricke, *Food Control*, 2015, **54**, 111.
4. F. Chemat, A. Sylvie, F. Tixier, A. M. A. Vian, T. Allaf and E. Vorobiev, *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 2015, **71**, 157.
5. H. Kusuma, D. Putri, I. Dewi and M. Mahfud, *Chemistry & Chemical Technology*, 2016, **10**, 213.
6. K. H. Rechinger, "*Flora Iranica*, Graz: Akademische Druck und Verlagsanstalt", 1982, Vol. 152.
7. M. D. Guillén and M. J. Manzanos, *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 1999, **79**, 1267.
8. K. D. Bauer, H. Garbe and H. Surburg, "Common fragrance and flavor materials", Wiley-VCH, Verlag, Germany, 1997.

Nematollahi: *Thymus fedtschenkoi* essential oils composition and their antioxidant activity etc.

9. M. Abousaber, M. Khanavi, M. Khoshchereh, A. Hadjiakhoondi, M. Shams Ardekani and A. Shafiee, *Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 2012, **1**, 34.
10. A. Gh. Pirbalouti, M. Hashemi and F. Taherian Ghahfarokhi, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2013, **48**, 43.
11. H. Ghelichnia, *Cercetări Agronomice în Moldova*, 2016, **2**, 107.
12. M. Pirigharnej, R. Heydari, S. Zare, J. Khara and R. Emam-Ali sabzi, *International Journal of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 2012, **4**, 92.
13. S. Khorasany, M. H. Azizi, M. Barzegar and Z. H. Esfahani, *Nutrition and Food Sciences Research*, 2016, **3**, 35.
14. F. A. Agili, *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 2014, **21**, 1670.
15. F. Mojab and B. Nickavar, *Planta Medica*, 2006, **18**, 272.
16. M. E. Lucchesi, F. Chemat and J. Smadja, *Journal of Chromatography A*, 2004, **1043**, 323.
17. R. P. Adams, "Identification of essential oil components by gas chromatography/quadrupole mass spectroscopy", 4th ed., Carol Stream Allured Publishing Corporation, USA, 2007.
18. L. Z. P. Ang, R. Hashim, S. F. Sulaiman, A. Y. Coulibaly, O. Sulaiman, F. Kawamura and K. M. Salleh, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2015, **76**, 755.
19. J. Safaei-Ghomi, A. H. Ebrahimabadi, Z. Djafari-Bidgoli and H. Batooli, *Food Chemistry*, 2009, **115**, 1524.
20. A. Sharifzadeh, A. Jebeli Javan, H. Shokri, S. Abbaszadeh and K. Keykhosravy, *Journal of Medical Mycology*, 2016, **26**, 11.

